

Investigating employee performance in higher education: The role of satisfaction and commitment

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ABSTRACT

The rapid transformation of education requires performance and innovation. This study aimed to examine the interconnectedness between organizational commitment (OC), job satisfaction (JS), and employee performance (EP) in higher education in Indonesia. EP is measured by how well you handle critical emergencies, how well you solve creative problems, how well you manage work stress, how well you handle uncertain and unpredictable work situations, and how well you adapt to other people. OC is measured by the strong desire to be an employee, the desire to work hard, acceptance of organizational values, acceptance of organizational goals, and work loyalty. JS is measured by the work itself, wages, promotion opportunities, supervision, and colleagues. The population in this study were all 150 employees of the Archive Bureau in Educational Colleges in Indonesia. In this study, researchers used the saturated sampling method as the basis for sampling, where all 150 members of the population were used as samples. A deeper comprehension of the connections between the variables was achieved by quantitatively applying structural equation modeling based on AMOS 21. The findings indicate that organizational commitment and job satisfaction positively influence employee performance in higher education in Indonesia. Indeed, job satisfaction among employees can enhance their performance. This study helps organizations perform better during COVID-19, particularly in higher education. The researcher suggests that additional researchers conduct larger-scale research on improving performance in areas like innovation and productive behavior.

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1. INTRODUCTION

One of the most important topics in the study of organizational behavior and human resource management is employee performance [1]–[3]. Effective employee performance is an indicator that the organization has adequate human resources. Human resource management performance is a determining factor for organizations to survive and grow during increasingly fierce competition between organizations [3]–[6]. The fact that employee performance is directly related to the success of each organizational activity chain, from upstream to downstream, provides the underlying explanation, from production activities to service activities to end-users. University performance by contributing to society in education, research, and community service.

Education, research, and community service will not run effectively when they are not reinforced by supporting services, such as library services, extracurricular activities, consultations, scholarships, and health to licensing services for all academicians [7]. Everything must be run synergistically and mutually support each other in a single supply chain [7], [8]. One of the most important services in promoting the success of higher education goals in terms of organizational administration is the university archive service [9]. In this case, archives have an essential function and role as a memory center, a source of information, and a monitoring tool for the entire chain of service activities, including assisting management in decision-making or policy formulation [7].

Archives as documents are produced or received by a person or organization during a business trip and stored by that person or organization [10], [11]. In contrast, archives as documents define them as organizational memory, decision-making material, and the foundation for legal defensibility [12]. In the context of higher education management, archiving institutions are an integral part of the higher education activity process. Without a good record of management, a university is at risk of losing transactional evidence, behavioral evidence and historical memory as well as losing valuable information in the form of knowledge and best practices from its human resource management behavior [13]. Therefore, archival institutions in universities play an important role [14] in identifying, storing, and protecting the intellectual assets of the organization [15]–[17].

The success of organizing archival activities at education universities depends heavily on human resources. However, there are still problems that are still the homework of the education university archival bureau. In this case, the existing human resources have not met the minimum criteria (standards) for employees who manage archives [18]. To present, the archival human resources at education universities have not been fully able to run the Dynamic Archives Information System (DAIS) effectively and optimally. There is still approximately 51.3% of archival management employees who experience difficulties in running DAIS. One of the reasons is the qualifications and educational backgrounds of archives employees, many of which do not match their duties as archive managers [19].

Educational institutions that are growing rapidly, need to anticipate changes. Therefore, service systems, performance, and effective operational models become intensive studies in organizational management. In the condition of COVID-19 [20], no institution or even a state could predict and prepare both economically and aspects of education services quickly [17]. It only switches to online services for developed nations, but developing nations that are not ready must choose between service system effectiveness and performance. As factors influencing performance, this study examines organizational commitment and job satisfaction as well as the process's impact during the crisis [10].

This study examines the performance of employees at the education archives institution. As one of the top public universities in Indonesia, especially in West Java, the performance is inseparable from the role and performance of existing archival institutions. It is impossible for a university's ranking to be separated from its archive management. According to prior researchers, the performance of employees at this archive institution can be one of the benchmarks in understanding the performance of the administration section on the education campus in general [12], [16]. In literature, many studies state that employee performance is closely related to organizational commitment [21]–[23] and job satisfaction [24], [25]. The responsibility of every representative to their association has an exceptionally cozy relationship with their exhibition. At the same time, job satisfaction and employee performance are closely linked [26].

Concerning organizational commitment, which demonstrates employees' desire to remain employed as well as their confidence in and acceptance of the organization's goals [24], equates that commitment with loyalty [27]. The majority of people understand commitment to be a never-ending process by which members of an organization express their concern for the success and goodness of the organization. Commitment is an attitude that leads to employee loyalty [22], [28]. Commitment to the organization, job satisfaction, and how they relate to employee performance at the education archive institution, are interesting to do when education faces two critical events. First, all existing universities are confronted with the COVID-19 pandemic, which hinders the work of all existing employees, including employees in the archive bureau. This condition produces exciting research findings, especially related to employees' organizational commitment, whether they still have a robust motivation to work or not. Then, from the performance side, we can determine whether they can adapt to the situation [29].

There are two types of tasks that employees are responsible for carrying out: technical-administrative tasks and performance on leadership tasks. Technical-administrative task performance, which includes planning, organizing, and managing daily work through technical skills and business evaluation, is the expected job performance [30]. Simultaneously, the presentation of authority undertakings is marked through defining key objectives, upholding the expected exhibition principles, and spurring and guiding subordinates to finish work through support, acknowledgment, and helpful analysis. Furthermore, employee performance can be measured according to the needs of their respective organizations so that the indicators

can be adjusted according to the organization's interests [31]. In this case, that performance measurement can be carried out using several indicators such as quantity work, quality work, dependability, initiative, adaptability, and cooperation [32]. This involves considering the ability to work with others [30].

The indicators used in this study were created by Stasielowicz. These indicators include being able to handle emergencies and crises, reducing stress at work, coming up with creative solutions to problems, coping with uncertain and unpredictable work situations, learning and self-training, interpersonal and cultural adaptability, and physical adaptability [33]. The consideration in choosing these indicators is because they measure things relevant to the context of employee performance in crises due to the COVID-19 pandemic. It includes relevant indicators like the ability to deal with emergencies and crises, control stress, deal with uncertain and erratic work situations, and physical adaptability.

Organizational commitment is characterized by self-assurance and acceptance of the organization's values and goals. A strong desire to continue working with the organization and a willingness to exert a lot of effort on its behalf are also required [34]. Employees with a robust affective commitment will stay in the organization out of desire, while those with a robust ongoing commitment and normative commitment will lead the organization out of necessity. The degree to which a person identifies with, participates in, and is unwilling to leave an organization is known as organizational commitment [35]. The degree to which a person adopts the values of the organization in order to identify issues in order to fulfill their job responsibilities is known as organizational commitment. Individual recognizable proof with contribution in the association is the general strength of authoritative responsibility. Hierarchical responsibility is a feeling of distinguishing proof, dependability, and inclusion revealed by a worker to an association or hierarchical.

A prior study explains that organizational commitment brings significant results such as high performance, low turnover rates, and low absenteeism rates [36], [37]. In addition, employee commitment is also related to other desired outcomes, such as perceptions of organizational climate, namely a warm and supportive organization and be a good, helpful team member. According to this definition, employee loyalty to the business is characterized by a firm belief in and acceptance of the business's goals and values, a willingness to put in more effort for the company, and a strong incentive to remain a member [38]. Several factors that influence organizational commitment are education level, position, and personality. To measure the variables of organizational commitment in this study, used four indicators were adjusted to the organization's performance during COVID-19 demanding rapid change is a strong desire for membership, the desire to great lengths to work, acceptance of the organization's value as well as its objectives [39].

A person's feelings about their job are reflected in their level of satisfaction. Job satisfaction is an individual's general attitude toward their job, or the difference between what a worker receives and what they think they should receive [40]. Work not entirely settled by a few variables, to be specific intellectually testing work, steady working circumstances, strong colleagues, and individual reasonableness for work. A person's general attitude toward their job is called job satisfaction [41]. Suardhita, Rafik, and Siregar stated that, "job satisfaction" is "a happy emotional state" or "strong emotions" that an individual encounters as a result of their work evaluation or experience [42]. Additionally, it is said that a person's level of job satisfaction reflects how they feel about their job, as evidenced by the significant attitude of workers toward their work and everything they encounter in the workplace.

Numerous benefits will accrue to the business in the event that it is able to influence employee satisfaction at work. With job satisfaction, work can be finished more quickly, damage can be lessened, attendance can be lower, employee movements can be reduced, work productivity can rise, and unit costs can be lower [43]. The indicators used to measure job satisfaction are pay, promotion, coworkers, nature of work, and supervision [44]–[46]. The extent to which technical assistance, attention, and encouragement are shown by the closest supervisor to the subordinates. Bosses who have good personal relationships with subordinates and are willing to understand the interests of their subordinates make a significant contribution to employee satisfaction and subordinate participation. There are four aspects to measuring job satisfaction: psychological, social, physical, and financial [47]. In reality, someone who feels satisfied will feel happy and comfortable in his environment to be motivated to perform at its best.

Throughout the COVID-19 pandemic, educational institutions in Indonesia made major changes in aspects of service and organizational performance. Various changes such as work attendance systems, online services, online learning, finance, and administration are quickly implemented from policy to operational aspects. This study complements the readiness for change and the performance of higher education institutions in adapting to changes, demands, and transformation of education. Based on the explanation and the following conceptual framework, the research hypotheses are provided as: i) H1: There is a positive and significant link between organizational commitment (OC) and employee performance (EP); ii) H2: There is a positive and significant link between organizational commitment and job satisfaction (JS); and iii) H3: There is a positive and significant link between job satisfaction and employee performance.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This research is a causal associative study using a quantitative approach. Employee performance is examined in this study in relation to job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Variables are arranged based on theories and hypotheses. Associative correlation seeks to find a causal relationship between related variables. The participants in this study were all employees of educational institutions' archives, consisting of civil servant employees, permanent employees, and non-permanent employees, totaling 150 people. Saturated sampling due to limited researchers to obtain data and access to higher education during the COVID-19. In this study, researchers used the saturated sampling method as the basis for sampling, where samples were taken from each of the 150 people in the population. In detail, the respondents involved in this study were dominated by male employees, with a percentage of 5%. The demographic participants also showed that the majority of employees were more than 50 years old (32%), followed by the employees aged 41-50 years old (28%). Based on education, the last education in high school was 16%, the latest diploma education was 2.2%, the last education was bachelor's degree was 75%, and the master's degree was 6.8%.

An online questionnaire was used to collect the data for this study, which were then analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. A 5-point Likert scale scoring system was used to analyze the collected data. Furthermore, testing the validity of the instrument using the free coefficient formula from Karl Pearson's product moment [48], [49]. The instrument can reveal something that the questionnaire will measure, so the validity test is used [50]. The reliability of each test is 0.859, 0.734, and 0.880, respectively, and all instruments are determined as valid and reliable. A reliability test is carried out to state the level of consistency of a test item [51] to measure it using Cronbach's alpha [52].

Using the Cronbach's criterion of either 0.70 or greater. In the theory-based causality model test, construct measurement model validity and reliability were evaluated [53]. Things meet the models on the off chance that the experimental outcomes show a revised all out thing relationship coefficient of no less than 0.40, or the Cronbach's alpha coefficient (α). If the coefficient is statistically significant, the indicators are shown to be valid for measuring the latent variable, and the questionnaire is shown to be reliable if the coefficient is not less than 0.70 (p -value <0.05), and the value in standardized numbers is not less than 0.50. A reliable measurement model measures the latent variable if the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) results can provide a minimum composite reliability (CR) value of 0.70 and an average variance extracted (AVE) value of not less than 0.50. In addition, the regression coefficient and correlation tests' normality, linearity, and significance are used in the hypothesis test. In order to test the goodness of fit (GOF) model, probability must satisfy a number of measurement criteria >0.5 [54], [55] root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) <0.05 [56], comparative fit index (CFI) >0.95 [56], and Chi-square/degree of freedom (CMIN/DF) values <2 [57]. Underlying condition displaying structural equation modeling (SEM) applies a concurrent examination model, a mix of exploratory variable investigation and corroborative component investigation. So that with SEM multiple linear regression simultaneously between variables and indicators can form a model.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In higher education, employee performance, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment are developed and measured in this study. The preparation of exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses is the process that is carried out. After obtaining the research results that meet the model criteria, it is continued with hypothesis testing based on research questions compiled from theory. The estimation of the initial model measurement's results the instrument as a measuring tool for research variables with a loading factor of <0.5 , thus it was not valid and excluded from the model. The measurements of all research variables with loading factors greater than 0.70, CR greater than 0.60, and AVE greater than 0.50 as displayed in Table 1.

Model of Employee Performance in Higher Education During the COVID-19 period, Independent variable=EP (X); Mediation variable=OC (M); Dependent variable=JS (Y). The preparation of the linear function equation of each variable aims to develop a path for analyzing the influence of variables, so that it can be used as a complete model in structural equation modeling. The results of the modeling are based on theoretical studies and expert opinions, as well as the hypotheses proposed by the researchers, the direct, indirect and total influence in this study with (1), (2), and (3).

$$Y = i1 + cX + e1 \quad (1)$$

$$M = i2 + aX + e2 \quad (2)$$

$$Y = i3 + c'X + bM + e3 \quad (3)$$

The measurement model for the COVID-19 period has then assessed the normality of the test results of employees' performance in higher education. The skewness statistic for all of the observed variables is between 2.58 and Critical Ratio, and they are all normally distributed. Amos is the sole source for the processing results and performance of higher education employees during the COVID-19 outbreak. Figure 1 depicts 21 as full model-standardized estimates.

Table 1. Result of exploratory factor analysis model measurement

No	Variable (Dimension and indicators)	λ	α	CR	AVE
1	Employee performance (EP)				
EP1	Handling critical emergencies	0.743			
EP3	Solving creative problems	0.675	0.86	0.87	0.58
EP4	Managing job stress	0.711			
EP6	Facing an uncertain and unpredictable work situation	0.907			
EP7	Interpersonal adaptation	0.767			
2	Organizational commitment (OC)				
OC1	Strong desire as employee	0.597			
OC2	Desire to try hard at work	0.825	0.73	0.84	0.51
OC3	Acceptance of organizational values	0.739			
OC5	Acceptance of organizational goals	0.733			
OC6	Work loyalty	0.667			
3	Job satisfaction (JS)				
JS1	The work itself	0.771			
JS4	Wages	0.563	0.88	0.82	0.56
JS5	Promotions opportunity	0.749			
JS6	Supervision	0.753			
JS8	Co-workers	0.634			

PERFORMANCE OF EMPLOYEES IN HIGHER EDUCATION DURING THE COVID-19 PERIOD
 Unstandardized estimates
 Chi-square = 67.278; df = 84; p = 0.909; Cmin/df = 0.801; RMSEA = 0.000;
 RMR = 0.095; AGFI = 0.923; CFI = 1.000; GFI = 0.946; TLI = 1.023

Figure 1. Results of the structural equation research model

This study measures OC, JS and EP. Based on unstandardized measurement estimates, with each loading factor above 0.7, it is determined that the EP variable is measured by dealing with critical emergencies, solving creative problems, managing work stress, and adapting to interpersonal situations, $\alpha=0.88$, $CR=0.82$, and $AVE=0.56$. The OC variable is measured by the strong desire to be an employee, the desire to work hard, acceptance of organizational values, acceptance of organizational goals, and work loyalty with each loading factor above 0.7, $\alpha=0.73$, $CR=0.84$, and $AVE=0.51$. The JS variable is measured by the work itself, wages, promotion opportunities, supervision, and colleagues with a loading factor above 0.7, $\alpha=0.88$, $CR=0.82$, and $AVE=0.56$ respectively.

Based on the data analysis criteria, the validity, reliability and item factor loading criteria have been fulfilled to be able to continue testing the model by conducting a SEM hypothesis analysis. The next step is to examine the effect between variables with a significance level >0.05 . These results describe the influence and the level of significance in this study. Based on the hypothesis and the results, Table 2 contains the test results for the performance of employees working in higher education during the COVID-19 period.

Table 2. Measurement model hypothesis test results

Hypothesis testing	Estimate		S.E.	C.R.	P	Result
	RW	SRW				
OC → JS	0.308	0.262	0.120	2.571	0.010	Significant
OC → EP	0.221	0.198	0.109	2.028	0.043	Significant
JS → EP	0.230	0.243	0.092	2.494	0.013	Significant

There were three hypotheses tested with success in this study, with a significant effect between OC on JS, OC on EP, and JS on EP, according to the results of the hypothesis test of the performance of employees in higher education during the COVID-19 period (Table 2). Furthermore, to meet the criteria for an acceptable model, it must meet the criteria of Goodness of fit (GOF). Modeling and measuring the influence between variables that meet GOF criteria can be used as a reference for standardized measurement models for future researchers. The main criterion in the GOF test is to fulfill the $p\text{-value} > 0.05$. Table 3 displays the GOF research model that was obtained.

Table 3. Goodness of fit test results

Test Statistics	Criteria	Value	Result
Chi-square	-	67.278	-
Degree of freedom	-	84	-
p-value	>0.05	0.909	Accepted
Cmin/DF	<2.00	0.801	Accepted
Root Mean Square Residual (RMR)	<0.05	0.095	Not accepted
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	<0.08	0.000	Accepted
Adjusted Goodness of Fit (AGFI)	>0.90	0.923	Accepted
Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)	>0.90	0.946	Accepted
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	>0.90	1.000	Accepted
Tucker Lewis Index (TLI)	>0.90	1.023	Accepted

Based on the Goodness of fit test, the research data show that the model meets the requirements for Goodness of fit. The findings were then analyzed for their direct and indirect effects to determine the effective effect of the path between models as a reference for this study. The Amos 21 research output data serve as the foundation for the conclusions as shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Direct, indirect, and total effect

	Direct effects			Indirect effects			Total effects		
	OC	JS	EP	OC	JS	EP	OC	JS	EP
JS	0.308	-	-	-	-	-	0.308	-	-
EP	0.221	0.230	-	0.071	-	-	0.292	0.230	-

The most extensive total effect coefficient, 0.308, was made possible by the direct and indirect effects that were derived from the output data for Amos 21. Based on Table 4, it is possible to draw the conclusion that improving employee performance in higher education during the COVID-19, it is necessary to have high job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Organizational commitment's total direct effect on employees' performance in higher education during the COVID-19 is greater than job satisfaction's mediating effect. Organizational commitment has a significant impact on employee performance, as this study demonstrated. The variable organizational commitment has a significant impact on employee performance. On the basis of these findings, it is possible to explain that an employee's job performance is correlated with their level of organizational commitment [58], [59]. Having a stronger desire to remain with the current organization and continues to aid in the achievement of objectives is fully engaged in their work because that work is a crucial means by which individuals can help the organization achieve its goals [60].

The same holds true for the claim that dedication to a solid organization can boost one's performance within the company [61], [62]. Authoritative responsibility is the level at which people take on the qualities and objectives of the association and relate to them in satisfying their work liabilities [63]. If employees have a strong belief in the values and objectives of the company, they can be inspired to perform at a higher level, are willing to work hard for the organization, and want to stay a member. Employee performance is significantly influenced by job satisfaction, which can be explained by the fact that higher levels of job satisfaction indicate improved performance [64], [65]. This means that having employee job satisfaction will be more efficient, productive, care about the organization and, have a partnership with the organization and allow employees to work better [66]. Employee performance is closely linked to job satisfaction because contented workers tend to be more focused on their assigned tasks, work quickly, are error-free, and always willing to take on more responsibility. This is an effective employee response that is the result of their experience at work [66]. Thus, if the job conditions support the employee's expectations, the employee will do his best, thereby combining the organizational goals with his. It follows from this description that employees are more likely to perform at their best when they are happy at work [67].

When both job satisfaction and organizational commitment are present simultaneously, employee performance is significantly impacted. This study demonstrates that job satisfaction and organizational commitment have a significant impact on employee performance. Based on the findings, it is possible to explain that an employee's performance will be influenced more by their level of organizational commitment and job satisfaction [67]. The research of is also bolstered by this study's findings [68], [69], which states that job satisfaction and organizational commitment have a significant impact on employee performance. In the meantime, employee performance is influenced in part by how satisfied they are with their job, as well as how committed they feel to their organization. These factors are also related to how much responsibility a person holds in their job and how well they are fulfilling their occupation's requirements [70]. The findings of this study are that education university employees have implemented daily check-in and check-out for work. The daily check is essential to see what the team will be working on that day. While daily checks are important to see what things have been done by the work team, assisted by meetings through Zoom webinars, learning, and self-training, being able to adapt and communicate according to the norms and values depending on the organization quickly.

4. CONCLUSION

The result found that having an organized job and being satisfied with one's job influence how well students perform in higher education in Indonesia. This study provides empirical evidence about how employees perform in higher education that JS in higher education needs to be improved through supervision. EP can be increased through solving creative problems, and OC can be increased through work loyalty. Indeed, job satisfaction can promote greater employee performance, organizational commitment and job satisfaction both affect employee performance. Commitment in the workplace can take many forms and has the potential to influence organizational effectiveness and employee performance. Better performance of the workforce is a result of the level of job satisfaction. If employees are not satisfied with their jobs, they may not be as committed to their work and may not achieve as much as they could. This can lead to decreased organizational performance and goals, work quickly, are free from errors and negligence, and are always willing to accept more responsibility. Become an organizational study during the COVID-19 period in optimization and work innovation and as a treasure trove of knowledge for the development of management disciplines in improving performance, as well as performance innovation during the pandemic case study at Education University as a higher education institution that follows rapid educational.

This study has several limitations, because it only focuses on one university with JS, OC, and EP as research variables. Some of the variables recommended by researchers include being able to examine innovative performance, modeling digital administrative effectiveness, the effect of giving rewards, work culture and transformational leadership. The researcher suggests further researchers to develop research on other variables and on a wider scale in improve the performance of employees in higher education.

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